

DESIGN AND PROTOTYPING OF COMPOSITE DEPLOYABLE BOOMS FOR SOLAR SAILS

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ABSTRACT

The solar sail is a promising propulsion concept that utilizes solar radiation pressure to navigate in space without propellant, enabling missions otherwise unattainable with traditional propulsion methods (e.g., electric or chemical propulsion). This paper presents the design of the structural subsystem of a 35x35 monolithic solar sail, with a specific focus on composite the deployable booms responsible for deploying and tensioning the sail membrane. Structural numerical analyses are conducted both on a full-scale model of a single boom and on the solar sail system. The former is intended to estimate the critical buckling load of the composite booms, the latter is used to determine the axial load acting on the boom tips due to membrane tension and to evaluate maximum sail displacements caused by solar radiation pressure. The axial load acting on the boom tip must remain below the critical buckling value, and the maximum displacement of the sail must not exceed 1% of the sail's side length. In this work, we designed composite deployable booms to meet these requirements and prototyped them at lab-scale.

1 INTRODUCTION

Solar sail propulsion systems have long been of great interest for space missions. Unlike chemical or electric propulsion, which require onboard propellants, solar sailing uses an external source of propulsion, harnessing the Sun's power through the momentum transfer of photons that impact and reflect off the membrane [1].

Spencer and co-authors provide a survey of the state-of-the-art of the solar sailing technology [2]. According to their work, the first advanced conceptual study dates to the late 1970s when the Jet Propulsion Laboratory designed a spacecraft that would make a rendezvous of Halley's Comet. Later, the DLR-ESA-INVENT carried out the first ground test of a fully deployable solar sail structure in 1999. During the test, four carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) booms were deployed with the four triangular segments of the sail [3]. In 2010, the interplanetary kite-craft accelerated by radiation of the Sun (IKAROS), sponsored by the JAXA, was launched and successfully deployed a 196 m² solar sail on route to Venus [4]. Meanwhile, NASA developed the Nano Sail-D mission to demonstrate both the deployment of a sail from a three-unit CubeSat and the sail capability of accelerating spacecraft de-orbiting thanks to the increased atmospheric drag. The first Nano Sail-D unfortunately underwent a launch failure, whereas its flight spare satellite, NanoSail-D2, successfully deployed a 10m²-sail from a three-unit CubeSat. However, the results were not those expected since NanoSail-D2 remained in orbit for 240 days before re-entry even if it was supposed to deorbit from the initial 650 km altitude in 70-120 days [5]. Likewise, the LightSail programme, by the Planetary Society, involved solar sail technology using three-unit CubeSat. During this programme, LightSail-1 successfully deployed a 32 m²-solar sail [6] and, for the first time, LightSail-2 exploited the solar radiation pressure to perform an

apogee raising from a low Earth orbit (LEO) [8]. On April 23, 2024, the NAS's mission Advanced Composite Solar Sail System (ACS3) featuring a square-shaped solar sail with an approximate 0 m side was launched and successfully deployment of the composite boom solar sail in LEO in August 2024 [7].

For solar sail missions, the general trend is to use four deployable booms to unfurl and tension the sail. Deployable booms can be categorized according to the cross-section geometry, the most popular being: Storable Tubular Extendible Member (STEM), Collapsible Tubular Mast (CTM), and Triangular Rollable and Collapsible (TRAC). A STEM is generally made of a thin-walled composite shell with circular cross-section [8], a CTM is made of two thin flexible shells with a bi-convex shape bonded at their edges cite [9,10] a TRAC is composed by two curved C-shaped section joined along one[11,12], and a SHEARLESS boom is formed by coupling the edges of two cylindrical shells front-to-front by a tightly-fitted outer sheath [13,14]. In this work, we consider CTMs.

The design of deployable booms serving as fundamental structural component in the solar sail system is particularly delicate. These booms must apply enough tension to the membrane to avoid significant out-of-plane deflections, while also withstanding compression without buckling. While numerical analysis can come at hand, structural simulations of solar sail systems often struggle with convergence due to the nonlinearities introduced by the large, thin membranes and the slender, flexible booms [15]. In 2002, Murphy and co-authors proposed a pre-tensioning method to solve convergence issues [16]. The pre-tensioning step allows the membrane to get out-of-plane stiffness to run the subsequent dynamic analysis and get the system's first ten natural modes. Talegani et al. maintained the same strategy and, in addition to predict the vibration modes, performed a geometrically nonlinear static analysis to evaluate the full-scale deformations of the pre-tensioned solar sail systems [17]. Sleight and Muheim performed a parametric study on a 150 m sail with a variable pre-stress at the center of its triangular segments (from 0.1 to 5 psi) [18]. After pre-tensioning, the sail deflection shows an inflection point as the pre-stress level increases from 1 to 3 psi, while the boom deflections increase continuously, as well as its compression level. Sleight and Muheim used a fictitious thermal load to contract the cables connecting the booms and the sail corners. Different thermal field results in a variable pre-tensioning scenario. Other methods were proposed to simulate pre-tensioning such as the quasi-random application of small out-of-plane forces to get a feasible static sail [19]. In this work, we use the pre-tensioning method with a fictitious thermal field.

In previously presented works, system-level models of solar sail structures often lack detail in the representation of individual booms. These components are frequently simplified as one-dimensional beams, with the material typically assumed to be isotropic, whereas in reality, booms are thin-walled shells that may exhibit local instabilities and are often made of composite materials with inherently anisotropic properties. In this work, we aim to investigate the behavior of the boom more thoroughly, treating it as an integral part of the solar sail structure. To this end, we perform a structural analysis of both a single boom and the full solar sail system, modeling the boom in both cases as a two-dimensional shell with anisotropic properties. Two full-scale finite element method (FEM) models are developed. The first is a model of the boom, aimed at evaluating its critical buckling load. The second is a system-level FEM model of the solar sail, consisting of the sail membrane and the boom acting as a support structure. This model is intended to assess the maximum out-of-plane displacement of the sail under solar radiation pressure. The buckling analysis results from the first analysis are then compared with the compression forces acting on the boom to verify whether the boom is truly capable of providing the required tensioning.

2 FINITE ELEMENT MODELS

This section describes the numerical model of the boom used to evaluate its buckling load and the numerical model of the solar sail system developed to identify the compression induced on the booms due to sail's tensioning and the deflection of the tensioned membrane due to solar pressure. The ABAQUS software has been used, which has been compared and validated against other finite element software [17].

2.1 BOOM FINITE ELEMENT MODEL

To ensure efficient impulse transfer and manoeuvrability, the membrane must be placed under tension. As a result, the booms are primarily subjected to axial compression, necessitating a buckling analysis. This analysis provides estimates of the critical load that would cause structural collapse, enabling the application of appropriate pre-tensioning.

The boom is modelled by sketching its cross-section geometry, shown in Fig. 1, where $r_1 = 39$ mm is the radius of the central arc segment, $r_2 = 18$ mm is the radius of the edge arc segment, $w = 6$ mm is the width of the flange, called web, and the subtended angle $\alpha_1 = \alpha_2 = 90^\circ$. The cross-section has then been extruded to a length of 24.75 m. This length was selected to be half of the diagonal of a 35 m square, as the CTMs are intended to support the 35-by-35 meter monolithic solar sail. The boom is modelled as two separate shells, bonded along the web region through tie constraints.

Figure 1. Geometric description on the composite boom.

The mesh consists of 60,500 shell-S4R elements for each shell. In this model, the edge points at the root cross-section are fully constrained in translation and rotation to simulate the interlocking with the bus. In contrast, the edge points at the tip cross-section are constrained in z-rotation only. Additionally, a unit load is applied at the CTM's tip.

The boom is made of a 2-ply composite laminate featuring an anti-symmetric lay-up with fiber orientations of $\pm 45^\circ$, a total thickness of 0.16 mm, and a density of 1371 kg/m³. The reinforcement is composed of 6k Toray T300 carbon fiber spread tows, woven into a plain weave fabric. The matrix is the CYTECH CYCOM® 823 epoxy. The mechanical behavior of such material is represented using the ABD stiffness matrix, initially computed via classical laminate theory (CLT). The ABD entries were subsequently refined based on an experimental characterization campaign conducted on specimens made from the same material system. The ABD matrix is as follows, where sub-matrix A is in N/m, while sub-matrix D is in Nm:

$$ABD = \begin{bmatrix} 4.357e+06 & 3.903e+06 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 3.903e+06 & 4.357e+06 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 4.074e+06 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 9.296e-03 & 8.327e-03 & 6.362e-03 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 8.327e-03 & 9.296e-03 & 6.362e-03 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 6.362e-03 & 6.362e-03 & 8.692e-03 \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

In this model, the edge points at the root cross-section are fully constrained in translation and rotation to simulate the interlocking with the bus. In contrast, the edge points at the tip cross-section are constrained in z-rotation only. Additionally, a load is applied at the CTM's tip.

The simulation consists of a preliminary linear buckling analysis, followed by a non-linear Riks analysis [14, 20]. In the linear analysis, a unit tip load is applied to the boom to determine its critical buckling load. This critical load is then used in the subsequent non-linear analysis, which is conducted on an imperfect geometry. Geometric imperfections are introduced by superimposing the first three buckling modes, obtained from the linear analysis, onto the undeformed boom geometry. The amplitudes of the mode shapes are scaled to 1%, 0.5%, and 0.25% of the laminate thickness for the first, second, and third modes, respectively. The non-linear analysis is performed using the arc-length method [21–23], with the load applied incrementally through adaptive step sizes.

2.2 SOLAR SAIL SYSTEM FINITE ELEMENT MODEL

The solar sail system is composed by four supporting booms, placed along the diagonals of a 35 m square solar sail. The sail is supported by four 20 cm cables, which simulate the connection between the booms and the sail. The inner ends of the cables are attached to the corners of the sail, while the outer ends are connected to the tips of the booms via MPCs. Interactions between the assembly parts are modelled through the *General contact giving a “Hard” Contact normal behavior which avoids penetration between their surfaces.

The sail is modeled as a membrane, whose section has a thickness of 2.5 μm [24]. The sail is discretized by M3D4R elements, which are 4 node quadrilateral membrane elements, with reduced integration and hourglass control.

Each cable is modelled as a wire with a circular cross-section of radius 1.58 mm. Cables are discretized by T3D2 elements which are 2-node linear 3-D truss.

The booms are modeled as shells. Its geometric description is given in subsection 2.1. The booms are discretized by S4R elements

The sail and the cables are made of Kapton and Kevlar respectively. Their density and mechanical properties are taken from literature, and they are given in Table 1 [17].

Properties		Kapton	Kevlar
E	[GPa]	2.48	62
ν	–	0.34	0.36
ρ	[Kg/m ³]	1425.2	1440.0

Table 1: Properties of Kapton and Kevlar [17]

The simulation consists of two steps. The first step is the sail tensioning, which involves providing the connection cables with a thermal field. This field is fictitious and acts on cables only, therefore the coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) is given only for Kevlar, with $\text{CTE} = 4.6 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$ [8]. A decrease in temperature causes the cables to contract, which results in tensioning the membrane. In this step, geometric non-linearity is considered. The second step involves applying solar pressure, where a pressure of $2.0334 \times 10^{-5} \text{ Pa}$ is applied to surface of the tensioned membrane facing the Sun.

The Interactions, loads and boundary conditions acting in the FEM model of the solar sail system are shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2. Interactions, loads and boundary conditions acting in the FEM model of the solar sail system.

A dynamic explicit procedure is used, with default values of automatic stabilization. The “improvedDTmethod” algorithm is used to improve the speed of the analysis, allowing to identify the critical time step and avoiding numerical singularities. To further control the analysis, a viscous pressure is introduced as damping effect, limiting the rise of the system kinetic energy and simulating a quasi-static analysis. The viscous pressure used is $3.6 \cdot 10^{-6}$, considering a c_v of $2 \cdot 10^{-2}$ accordingly to Mallikarachchi and Pellegrino’s work [25].

3 RESULTS

This section presents both the results of the simulation at the individual component level and at the system-level. The results at the system-level are reported separately for the two consecutive analysis steps: the pre-tensioning and the solar pressure loading results are provided in Sec.3.2.1 and Sec.3.2.2, respectively.

3.1 BOOM FINITE ELEMENT MODEL RESULTS

Firstly, results of the mesh sensitivity analysis are reported in Fig. 3. The starting mesh was composed of about 30000 elements, with an approximate global size of 2 cm. It’s shown that the critical buckling load converges at a value of about 1.71 N for a number of elements greater than 60500 for each boom, which is an optimal trade-off between computational time and results accuracy. Such a mesh determined a critical load of 1.7018 N, deviating from the convergence value by approximately 0.65%. The first three buckling modes are presented in Fig. 3.

Figure 3. First three linear buckling modes; from the left: 1.7018 N, 1.7607 N, 15.318 N.

The Riks analysis yields the force at the tip vs. tip displacement curve, shown in Fig. 4. The maximum of the curve determines the buckling load of the first mode. The non-linear simulation shows that instabilities occurred at about 1.696 N, reaching 99.7% of the axial load computed in the linear analysis.

Figure 4. Axial load vs tip displacement curve by the nonlinear buckling analysis.

3.2 SOLAR SAIL SYSTEM FINITE ELEMENT MODEL RESULTS

In Sec.3.2.1 the minimum stress of the membrane due to the pre-tensioning is provided after a sensitivity analysis. Tensioning the sail will cause its stretching. So, the displacement fields are presented as well to evaluate how much and in which directions the membrane is stretched. Subsequently, in Sec.3.2.2 we present the displacements obtained from the solar radiation pressure application to the tensioned system. In plane and out-of-plane fields are evaluated for the membrane, showing very small deformation and therefore the capability of the proposed design to operate properly in the working.

3.2.1 Pre-tensioning results

In Fig. 5 shows the stress distribution over the sail after the pre-tensioning step is shown, where it was determined that a thermal load of -500°C is consistent with the loads observed on the sail surface. Indeed, a stress intensification is registered at the four corners of the sail, with a maximum value of about 2.2 MPa, while the remainder of the membrane is stretched with a stress of the order of Kpa, that

are compatible with the sail material properties, as established in [24]. At this point, the stress over the cables is 49 KPa, that induce a tensioning force on the boom tip of 0.38 N, preserving the integrity of the structure as the nonlinear critical load is about 1.696 N.

Figure 5. Mises stress distribution over the sail after pre-tensioning phase.

The in-plane displacement observed are less than 1 mm, denoting that the membrane is practically flat and stretched over all the surface, as shown in Fig. 6. Since the sail was defined with membrane-type elements, the out-of-plane displacements cannot be computed without an orthogonal load.

Figure 6. In-plane displacements of the sail after pre-tensioning phase: horizontal displacement on the left, vertical displacement on the right.

3.2.2 Solar pressure loading results

After the application of the solar radiation pressure, perpendicularly to the sail surface, the stress level changed slightly, preserving the same distribution of the previous step as reported in Fig. 7. The stress

value on the cables is slightly reduced compared to the simple tensioning phase; consequently, the boom structures will be able to sustain the overall load computed in the nonlinear analysis avoiding buckling occurrence.

Figure 7. Mises stress distribution over the sail after solar pressure loading.

Similarly, the in-plane displacements are substantially unchanged, Fig. 8, while a negative out-of-plane displacement is observed, aligned to the solar radiation pressure. Due to the presence of the boom structure behind the solar sail, the contact region is identified and highlighted in the contour plot in Fig. 9.

Figure 8. In-plane displacements of the sail after solar pressure loading: horizontal displacement on the left, vertical displacement on the right.

Figure 9. Out-of-plane displacement over the sail after the solar pressure loading.

4. LAB-SCALE BOOM PROTOTYPING

Lab-scale CTMs, each 70 cm in length and with a cross-section featuring all characteristic dimensions scaled at a 2:3 ratio compared to the reference design, were fabricated using a two-step, out-of-autoclave curing process. The two composite shells were cured separately and subsequently bonded together during a second curing cycle.

For each shell, the laminate lay-up and consumable layers were manually draped over a custom-designed mold, Fig. 10.

Figure 10. Customized mold for out-of-autoclave boom manufacturing.

The lay-up was then vacuum-bagged together with the mold, and the curing was performed using a feedback-controlled thermal system. This system consists of electric heating cartridges for heat input, a thermocouple for temperature monitoring, and a proportional-derivative temperature controller that regulates current flow to the cartridges. The heating cartridges are inserted into a through-hole running along the axis of the mold, while the thermocouple is placed directly on the mold surface to accurately track its temperature. The temperature controller is positioned for easy access and operation throughout the curing process. The components are shown in Fig. 11.

Figure 11. Feedback thermal control system.

The temperature cycle set at the temperature controller is the curing cycle as established per data sheet of CYCOM®823 RTM. (Cure temperature: 125°C, Cure time: 60 mins, Heat up rate: 2°C/min, Pressure: 0bar). At the end of the first cure, the shells were allowed to cool to room temperature and the demolding was performed. Then, a single ply of structural adhesive AF163 – 2K was used to bond together the two shells along their edges, with a cure cycle of 60 mins at 135°C.

In Fig. 12 the manufacturing steps are presented alongside and the prototype, which is characterised by a mean thickness of 0.16 mm.

Figure 12. Subsequent steps of boom manufacturing: shell curing cycle with vacuum bag lay-up, adhesive curing cycle, finished boom prototype.

9 CONCLUSIONS

In this work, the design for the boom supporting a 35 by 35 monolithic solar is presented, investigating its structural performances. First of all, the boom critical load at buckling is evaluated. Then the structural behaviour of the solar sail at a system level is investigated. A pre-tensioning value is selected such that the sail achieves stiffness without compromising the boom stability, i.e., compression load acting on the boom tip smaller than its critical buckling value. Within the limits of the maximum stress the sail can sustain, a load on the cables of 0.38 N is reached and the integrity of the boom structures is preserved. Finally, the out-of-plane displacements of the tensioned sail after the application of the solar radiation pressure are evaluated showing negligible deflections. Indeed, the out-of-plane maximum displacements of the membrane is about 3 mm, and the membrane-sail can be considered satisfactorily flat, thus providing a proper solar thrust. Based on these promising results a lab-scale boom prototype has been developed using an out-of-autoclave manufacturing process. Particularly, a two-step technique is proposed, realizing the two half shells of the boom and bonding them with a structural adhesive. The final prototype presents a mean thickness of 0.16 mm and well-aligns with the nominal curvature provided by the mold.

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